

Moderation effect of Socio-demographic factors in between physical health problems, mental health problems and presenteeism

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Abstract

This paper studies the moderation effect of socio-demographic factors in between physical health problems, mental health problems and presenteeism. It also studies the relationship between physical health problems, mental health problems and presenteeism. Data were collected from 375 employees working in public sector manufacturing organisation. The researcher chooses socio demographic variables age, gender, marital status, experience, education qualification and family income level as moderating variable. The results show that gender and marital status working as moderating variable in between physical health problems and presenteeism. Furthermore, the study results show that age, experience, education qualification and family income level not working as moderating variable in between physical health problems and presenteeism. This study confirms that physical health problems and presenteeism are significantly related and mental health problems and presenteeism are not significantly related.

Key words

Presenteeism, Physical health problems, Mental health problems, Socio demographic factors

Introduction

In 1994, Cary Cooper, a psychologist specialising in organisational management, coined the term "presenteeism." Presenteeism refers to the practise of reducing employee productivity at work due to mental, emotional, or physical issues (Burton, Conti, Chen, Schultz, Edington 1999). Employees who are sick are still present on the job, but they are less productive. The cost of absenteeism is straightforward, but the cost of presenteeism is more complicated. Companies have taken presenteeism into account in recent decades due to the high cost category (Lerner, Amick, Roger, Malspeiz, Bungay and Cynn 2001). Presenteeism research has recently expanded as a result of several studies demonstrating that the cost of presenteeism when related with absenteeism is greater than absenteeism. Health issues are a common occurrence in people's lives. The majority of companies around the world offer sick leave to employees who have health issues, as well as medical insurance, reimbursement, medical leave, and other benefits to employees who have health issues. Employees may go to work when they are sick due to work pressure or other situations resulting from changes in the organization's working environment.

This tendency will have an effect on employee performance, and the reason for their presence is frequently unknown, which was considered in this study. As a result, a comprehensive measure of presenteeism that contains information on presenteeism determinants is urgently required. Because extensive studies on presenteeism are not conducted in countries such as India, a comprehensive measure of presenteeism is useful. Furthermore, presenteeism terminology must be agreed upon, and presenteeism factors remain unstudied. This survey was conducted among public sector manufacturing organisations in the Indian state of Kerala. As government-owned businesses, public sector undertakings are founded, managed, and controlled by the Government of India or state governments. Government-owned businesses have a significant impact on the Indian economy. These government-owned enterprises were formed with the goal of alleviating poverty and underdevelopment by entering the major industrial sector. As a result, the new problem or phenomenon centred on government-owned businesses. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, this is the first major study on presenteeism in India. Based on a research gap, this study investigates the relationship between health problems and presenteeism, as well as the moderating variables in the relationship between health problems and presenteeism. Testable hypotheses were developed and data from the field survey were analysed to test these hypotheses. The majority of earlier presenteeism studies used samples from the United States and Europe (Lin and Lu, 2013). Samples are being collected from a varied population with a wide range of socio-cultural backgrounds for this investigation. This study fills a gap in the literature on presenteeism by including empirical data from a diverse population in India. Furthermore, this study fills a research gap on the variables of presenteeism and adds to the presenteeism literature.

Presenteeism and Health

Several studies have been conducted on the relationship between health and absenteeism (Chatterji, Tilley 2002, Burton et al 2004, Stewart et al 2003), but there has been less research on employee performance and presenteeism. Poor work performance is exacerbated by a variety of health issues (Schwart et al 1997, Stewart et al 2003). Health concerns are the leading cause of presenteeism-related productivity loss (Johns, 2010). Several studies are being conducted in this area to determine which health conditions influence presenteeism. Some of the health conditions affecting employee performance were arthritis (Goetz et al 2004), back or neck discomfort, musculoskeletal problems, migraines, many frequent headaches, allergies, asthma, and depression (Goetz et al 2004). It highlights the importance of treating presenteeism as a health issue. Other health-related disorders, such as chronic pain (Canadian 2006), hypertension (Wang

et al., 2003), and cardiac diseases, have a negative impact on employee performance. Respiratory or lung diseases, diabetes (Collins et al 2005), high cholesterol, obesity, sleep issues, chronic fatigue / low energy, and anxiety all have an impact on employee performance (Kessler et al., 2008). Allergies, asthma, depression (Goetz et al 2004), cancer (Wang et al 2003), stress (Pandey, 2020), drug/alcohol use (Thorrisen et al 2019), and sinusitis (Burton et al 2001) are all factors that affect job performance. Table no: 1 contains physical and mental health conditions most associated with presenteeism across numerous published studies. The standard errors were included. The majority of studies focus on presenteeism caused by chronic conditions (Schultz and Edington 2007). The bulk of the risk factors linked to presenteeism lacked sufficient data to draw any conclusions, and there are four statistical risk factors linked to presenteeism: 1. Influenza-related behaviour, 2. Socio-demographic factors, 3. Employment characteristics, and 4. Health (Webster et al., 2019). As a result, there is a research gap in the association between health problems and presenteeism and socio-demographic factors and presenteeism.

Table No: 1

Occurrence of Health Conditions Associated with Presenteeism from Multiple Sources and Occupations

Health Condition	Prevalence (%)	SE	Source
Arthritis	15.2	1.8	Goetzl, 2004
Back or neck pain	25.1	0.9	Goetzl, 2004
Other musculoskeletal disorder	33.5	1.8	Goetzl, 2004
Migraines, severe/frequent headaches	17.7	0.7	Goetzl, 2004
Chronic pain	23.6	NA*	Canadian, 2006
Hypertension	14.9	0.7	Wang, 2003
Heart disease	11.9	NA*	Collins, 2005
High cholesterol	20.0	0.5	Kessler, 2008
Stomach or intestinal ulcers	1.9	NA*	Collins, 2005
Other gastrointestinal problems	8.1	0.3	Kessler, 2008
Allergies	31.2	1.8	Goetzl, 2004
Asthma	10.2	0.5	Goetzl, 2004
Other respiratory or lung problem	1.3	NA*	Collins, 2005
Diabetes	3.8	0.4	Collins, 2005
Obesity	5.9	0.3	Kessler, 2004
Sleep problem	8.6	0.3	Kessler, 2008

Chronic fatigue/low energy	6.4	0.3	Kessler, 2008
Cancer	1.7	0.2	Wang, 2003
Anxiety	5.6	0.3	Kessler, 2008
Depression	9.4	0.6	Goetzl, 2004

Source: Warren, Carol L., "Cost Burden of the 'Presenteeism' Health Outcome in a Diverse Nurse and Pharmacist Workforce: Practice Models and Health Policy Implications" (2009). Theses and Dissertations (ETD). Paper 295. <http://dx.doi.org/10.21007/etd.cghs.2009.0345>.

Presenteeism and Socio-demographic factors

According to a previous study (Aronsson & Gustafsson, 2005), gender influences presenteeism, which is part of Johns' presenteeism model's personal variables area. Some of the socio-demographic factors that influence presenteeism behaviour are age (Bellaby, 1999; Aronsson & Gustafsson, 2005), income and education (Sturm and Gresenz 2002), marital status (Flor, Turk, Rudy 1989), and family status (Bellaby, 1999; Aronsson & Gustafsson, 2005). (Hansen & Andersen, 2008). Furthermore, the study discovered that more experienced employees are unaffected by presenteeism, implying that experience moderates the relationship between presenteeism and performance (Martinez and Ferreira, 2012). Three high-quality studies (Bracewell et al., 2010) revealed no link between age and presenteeism, however three additional studies found a link between younger age and presenteeism (Chambers et al., 2017). These findings emphasize the need of looking into the link between age and absenteeism in a distinct cohort. Two studies on gender and presenteeism (Bracewell et al, 2010) discovered a link between female gender and presenteeism, while three studies showed no link (Chambers et al., 2017). However, there is a relationship between presenteeism and financial worries (Chiu et al., 2017).

Methodology

In this study, the relationship between health problems (independent variable) and presenteeism (dependent variable) was examined utilizing a descriptive research methodology. It is a quantitative descriptive research approach because the Likert scale was used to measure all of the study's variables. Descriptive survey research, according to Saunders et al. (2003), carefully examines the event as it occurs and then accurately represents what the researcher sees. As a result, this study employs the survey research methodology. 21 illnesses or conditions were chosen as health factors by expert panels from a range of sources. Six sociodemographic variables were considered as moderating variables.

H_0^1 : There is no relationship between physical health problems and presenteeism

H_1^1 : There is a relationship between physical health problems and presenteeism

H_0^2 : There is no relationship between mental health problems and presenteeism

H_1^2 : There is a relationship between mental health problems and presenteeism

H_1^3 : The relationship between physical health problems and presenteeism is moderated by age

H_1^4 : The relationship between physical health problems and presenteeism is moderated by gender

H_1^5 : The relationship between physical health problems and presenteeism is moderated by marital status

H_1^6 : The relationship between physical health problems and presenteeism is moderated by qualification

H_1^7 : The relationship between physical health problems and presenteeism is moderated by experience

H_1^8 : The relationship between physical health problems and presenteeism is moderated by family income level

The sample frame was created using data from the Department of Industries and Commerce and the CAG report on public sector undertakings in Kerala for 2015–16. The Department of Industries and Commerce of the Kerala Government, which is also referred to as manufacturing in the CAG report on public sector undertakings in Kerala during 2015–16, was the first criterion examined for the establishment of a sample frame and also considered were organisations that had at least ten years' worth of financial data submitted for CAG audits. The second criterion for public-sector manufacturing organisations is the presence of at least one manufacturing facility. The third requirement was that the organisation be active or operational, as opposed to closed, inactive, liquidated, or non-operational. Based on the three criteria outlined here, twenty-two manufacturing public sector organisations were chosen as the sampling frame. These 22 organisations represent the chemical, electrical, ceramics and refractories, electronics,

engineering, textiles, and wood/agricultural sectors. As a result, the research's sampling frame, or working population, includes 22 organisations and their 9851 employees, giving the investigation enough scope. The census method was used to choose public-sector manufacturing units from the sampling frame. The type of sampling method utilised to select a sample from each organisation is simple random sampling. The number of respondents drawn from each unit is in the same proportion they occur in the population. The desired sample size from each organisation was determined using lottery approach in the simple random sampling. As a result, all of the approaches used in this study ensured that the sampling error was kept to a minimum, resulting in a precise conclusion. Here a subset of the population, which means sample, as per calculation got as 370 at a confidence level of 95% and margin of error 5%. The sample size was increased 10% to recoup for probable non responses (Martinez-meza et al., 2014). The sample size was then increased to 410 and after dropping the invalid and incomplete responses the final sample size of 375 reached at a response rate of 91%. The sample size was calculated with the help of the survey monkey platform. This sample size was confirmed through two other online platforms Raosoft calculator and open epi (Version 3.01). In this research, the researcher used both primary and secondary source for data collection. The primary data was collected with the help of different data collection instruments and secondary data was collected through books, journals, thesis and websites. A method called a self-administered structured questionnaire was used to collect the primary data in this investigation. Stanford presenteeism scale and as well as questionnaires on health were employed in this study. The questionnaires were closed-ended and used a five-point Likert scale to assess responses. Based on the available literature stanford presenteeism scale was found as the best acceptable questionnaire among a series of questionnaires for measuring the dependent variable presenteeism, The additional questionnaire were created with the use of literature study, an expert opinion process, and validity and reliability testing. Expert review is a relatively quick and cost-effective method of evaluating questionnaires (Presser et al., 1994). The surveys comprised the questions with the highest number of expert approvals. According to Ospina et al., (2015) Stanford presenteeism scale (SPS-6) has a acceptable level of proof for the mainstream measurement domains including internal consistency, content validity, convergent validity, construct validity and responsiveness. The Cronbach's alpha (.83) of the scale indicates adequate reliability and factor analysis shows a valid result (.98). Validity of the questionnaires was approved by the expert opinion method and

the reliability of the questionnaires was measured with Cronbach's alpha. Cronbach's alpha for health problems questionnaire is .787 and the validity of the health questionnaire was approved by an expert panel of Doctors. Percentage analysis, t-tests, ANOVAs, regression, and correlation tests were among the methods used to evaluate the data in SPSS. The moderation analysis was done with the processv3.5 by Andrew F Hayes through SPSS.

Analysis and Interpretation

Demographic Statistics

In this section the statistical analysis of basic demographic factors were interpreted. The basic demographic factors like age, gender, marital status, highest qualification, experience, family monthly income and residence were analysed. The percentage analysis was done for above explained demographic factors. In this study 5.6% respondents were in age up to 30, 41.6% in between 31-40, 30.7% in between 41-50 and 22.1 % in between 51-60. The highest number of respondents were lying in between the age category of 31-40 and lowest from age up to 30. The major respondents were from male category consists of 76.3% and female category consists of the least with 23.7%. This statistics shows major employees working in public sector manufacturing organisation were from male segment. The marital status of respondents consists of 7.7% single, 88.5% are married and 3.7% were divorced. Majority of respondents participated in this study are married one. About highest qualification of respondents 12.5% had highest qualification SSLC, 28.3% ITI qualification, 22.1% Diploma/Plus two qualification, 22.9% degree qualification and 14.1 % respondents highest qualification was post graduation. Statistics shows that majority of employees qualification were ITI and Diploma/plus two. The technical qualified employees were occupying majority in public sector manufacturing organisations. About experience of respondent 16.5% had experience up to 5, 23.7% respondent in experience range of 6-10, 36.5 % in experience range of 11-20, 19.5% in 21-30 and 3.7 % respondents had experience above 30. The majority of employees experience lying in between 6-20 years. Analysis shows 7.2% employees participated in the study had income up to 15000 Indian rupee monthly, 57.9% in between monthly income 15001-30000, 25.9% in between 30001-45000, 5.1% in between income range of 45001-60000 and 4% respondent had monthly income in Indian rupee above 60000. Majority of employees monthly income lying in between 15001-30000 Indian rupees. Majority of respondents participated in this study were from urban area i.e. 54.4% and

45.6% respondents from rural area. The demographic profiles of the respondents are depicted in Table No.2.

Table No: 2
Demographic profile

Demographic category	Count	Percent
Age		
Up to 30	21	5.6
31-40	156	41.6
41-50	115	30.7
51-60	83	22.1
Total	375	100.0
Gender		
Male	286	76.3
Female	89	23.7
Total	375	100.0
Marital Status		
Single	29	7.7
Married	332	88.5
Divorced	14	3.7
Total	375	100.0
Qualification		
SSLC	47	12.5
ITI	106	28.3
Diploma/Plus two	83	22.1
Degree	86	22.9
PG	53	14.1
Total	375	100.0
Experience		
Up to 5	62	16.5
6-10	89	23.7
11-20	137	36.5
21-30	73	19.5
Above 30	14	3.7
Total	375	100.0
Family Income level		

Up to 15000	27	7.2
15001-30000	217	57.9
30001-45000	97	25.9
45001-60000	19	5.1
Above 60000	15	4.0
Total	375	100.0

Analysis and Interpretations

Analysis of relationship between health problems and presenteeism based on health problems classification according to health conditions

The health problems were classified into two, physical health problems and mental health Problems. Gosselin and Lauzier (2011) mentioned the characteristics of presenteeism through two types of health problems, physical health problems and mental health problems. The relationship analysis was done based on these classifications. The primary objective of this research was to identify the relationship between physical health problems, mental health problems and presenteeism. Correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between independent variable physical health problems and dependent variable presenteeism and regression analysis was used to find model fit.

Physical health problems and presenteeism

Relationship with physical health problems and presenteeism was analysed and shows a correlation value of .145 and $p=.005$ in table no.4. The significant value shows that, there is a relationship

between

physical

health

problems and presenteeism.

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
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Table No: 3

Physical health problems and presenteeism descriptive statistics

Presenteeism	20.9787	4.62781	375
Physical health problems	25.0600	6.33500	375

Table No: 4
Correlation analysis between Physical health problems and presenteeism

		Presenteeism	Physical health problems
Presenteeism	Pearson Correlation	1	.145**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.005
	N	375	375
Physical health problems	Pearson Correlation	.145**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.005	
	N	375	375

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Regression analysis between physical health problems and presenteeism

The regression analysis between physical health problems and presenteeism shows an R value of .145, R squared value of .021. The ANOVA analysis shows an f value of 7.955 and sig vale of .005. The coefficient analysis shows t value of 2.820 for health and sig value .005. The significant value shows model applied, statistically predict the dependent variable. The results are shown in table no.5,6,7.

Table No: 5

Model Summary physical health problems and presenteeism									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.145 ^a	.021	.018	4.585	.021	7.955	1	373	.005

a. Predictors: (Constant), Physical health problems

Table No: 6

ANOVA physical health problems and presenteeism						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	167.250	1	167.250	7.955	.005 ^b
	Residual	7842.579	373	21.026		
	Total	8009.829	374			
a. Dependent Variable: Presenteeism						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Physical health problems						

Table No: 7

Coefficients of physical health problems and presenteeism						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	18.334	.967		18.954	.000
	Physical health problems	.106	.037	.145	2.820	.005
a. Dependent Variable: Presenteeism						

Mental health problems and Presenteeism

The relationship with mental health problems and presenteeism was analysed and shows a correlation value of $-.051$ and $p=.325$. The significant value shows that there is no relationship between mental health problems and presenteeism. The results are shown in table no.9.

Table No: 8

Descriptive Statistics of mental health problems and presenteeism

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Presenteeism	20.98	4.628	375
Mental health problems	4.08	1.752	375

Table No: 9
Correlations of mental health problems and presenteeism

Variables		Presenteeism	Mental health problems
Presenteeism	Pearson Correlation	1	-.051
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.325
	N	375	375
Mental health problems	Pearson Correlation	-.051	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.325	
	N	375	375

Physical health problems and its relationship with Presenteeism with moderating variables

The moderation effect of variables age, gender, marital status, qualification, experience and family income level on relationship between physical health problems and presenteeism was conducted and depicting below. For these moderation analyses 5000 samples were bootstrapped with 95% of confidence interval. The widely accepted Johnson-Neyman technique and dominant method -1SD, Mean, +1SD was used when probing interaction in linear model.

Physical health problems and its relationship with presenteeism is moderated by age

The relationship between physical health problems and presenteeism is moderated by age category was analysed. The moderating analysis was conducted using Hayes process in SPSS. Relationship of physical health problems and presenteeism among employees in public sector manufacturing organisations is moderated by age variable was analysed. The model summary recommends that physical health problems and interaction of age mutually explains 6.51% variance in presenteeism. The p-value=.0000 of the model shows that model is statistically significant. The moderating analysis with age shows a p-value of .4906 ($P > .05$) and LLCI (-.1134) and ULCI (.0545) values. These values indicate age not working as a moderator in between physical health problems and presenteeism (Table No: 10).

Table No: 10
Physical health problems and presenteeism is moderated by age

Run MATRIX procedure:
***** PROCESS Procedure for SPSS Version 3.5 *****

Written by Andrew F. Hayes, Ph.D. www.afhayes.com
Documentation available in Hayes (2018). www.guilford.com/p/hayes3

```

*****
Model : 1
  Y : PST
  X : PHT
  W : Age

Sample Size: 375
*****
OUTCOME VARIABLE: PST
Model Summary
      R      R-sq    MSE      F      df1    df2      p
      .2551   .0651  20.1849  8.6078  3.0000  371.0000  .0000

Model
      coeff      se      t      p    LLCI    ULCI
constant  21.0171   .2386  88.0921  .0000  20.5479  21.4862
PHT        .0745   .0386   1.9308  .0543  -.0014   .1504
Age       1.1399   .2733   4.1710  .0000   .6025   1.6773
Int_1     -.0295   .0427  -.6900  .4906  -.1134   .0545
Product terms key:
Int_1 :    PHT    x    Age

Test(s) of highest order unconditional interaction(s):
      R2-chng      F      df1    df2      p
X*W   .0012   .4761   1.0000  371.0000  .4906
-----
Focal predict: PHT    (X)
Mod var: Age    (W)

Data for visualizing the conditional effect of the focal predictor:
Paste text below into a SPSS syntax window and execute to produce plot.
DATA LIST FREE/
  PHT    Age    PST    .
BEGIN DATA.
-6.3353  -.8771  19.3815
.0000   -.8771  20.0172
6.3353  -.8771  20.6530
-6.3353  .0000  20.5449
.0000   .0000  21.0171
6.3353  .0000  21.4892
-6.3353  .8771  21.7084
.0000   .8771  22.0169
6.3353  .8771  22.3253
END DATA.
GRAPH/SCATTERPLOT=PHT WITH PST BY Age .
***** ANALYSIS NOTES AND ERRORS *****

```

Level of confidence for all confidence intervals in output: 95.0000
 NOTE: The following variables were mean centered prior to analysis: Age PHT
 ----- END MATRIX -----

Physical health problems and its relationship with presenteeism is moderated by gender

The relationship between physical health problems and presenteeism is moderated by gender category was analysed. The moderating analysis was conducted using Hayes process in SPSS. Relationship of physical health problems and presenteeism among employees in public sector manufacturing organisations is moderated by gender variable was analysed. The model summary recommends that physical health problems and interaction of gender mutually explains 6.25% variance in presenteeism. The p-value=.0000 of the model shows that model is statistically significant. The moderating analysis with gender shows a p-value of .0003 (P<.05) and LLCI (-.4338) and ULCI (-.1322) values. These values indicate gender working as a moderator in between physical health problems and presenteeism. The analysis shows in conditional effects first condition is significant (P value=.0000) and second condition (p=.3898) is not significant among the values of the moderator. The moderator gender has a significant conditional effect on relationship between physical health problems and presenteeism (Table No:11) and the graphical plot depicting conditional effects are generated (Graph No: 1).

Table No: 11
 Physical health problems and presenteeism is moderated by gender

```
Run MATRIX procedure:
***** PROCESS Procedure for SPSS Version 3.5 *****
      Written by Andrew F. Hayes, Ph.D.    www.afhayes.com
      Documentation available in Hayes (2018). www.guilford.com/p/hayes3
*****
Model : 1
  Y : PST
  X : PHT
  W : Gender

Sample Size: 375
*****
OUTCOME VARIABLE: PST
Model Summary
      R      R-sq    MSE      F      df1    df2      p
      .2501   .0625   20.2394   8.2513   3.0000  371.0000   .0000
Model
      coeff      se      t      p    LLCI    ULCI
constant  21.9129   .7319  29.9407   .0000  20.4738  23.3521
```

PHT	.5148	.1137	4.5288	.0000	.2913	.7383
Gender	-.6259	.5652	-1.1073	.2689	-1.7373	.4856
Int_1	-.2830	.0767	-3.6898	.0003	-.4338	-.1322

Product terms key:

Int_1 : PHT x Gender

Test(s) of highest order unconditional interaction(s):

	R2-chng	F	df1	df2	p
X*W	.0344	13.6146	1.0000	371.0000	.0003

Focal predict: PHT (X)

Mod var: Gender (W)

Conditional effects of the focal predictor at values of the moderator(s):

Gender	Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
1.0000	.2318	.0484	4.7854	.0000	.1365	.3270
2.0000	-.0512	.0595	-.8609	.3898	-.1681	.0657

Data for visualizing the conditional effect of the focal predictor:

Paste text below into a SPSS syntax window and execute to produce plot.

```
DATA LIST FREE/ PHT Gender PST .
```

```
BEGIN DATA.
```

```
-6.3353 1.0000 19.8185
.0000 1.0000 21.2870
6.3353 1.0000 22.7555
-6.3353 2.0000 20.9855
.0000 2.0000 20.6611
6.3353 2.0000 20.3368
```

```
END DATA.
```

```
GRAPH/SCATTERPLOT=
```

```
PHT WITH PST BY Gender .
```

```
*****ANALYSIS NOTES AND ERRORS*****
```

Level of confidence for all confidence intervals in output: 95.0000

NOTE: The following variables were mean centered prior to analysis: PHT

```
----- END MATRIX -----
```

Graph No: 1

Moderating effect of gender on relationship between physical health problems and presenteeism

Physical health problems and its relationship with presenteeism is moderated by marital status

The relationship between physical health problems and presenteeism is moderated by marital status category was analysed. The moderating analysis was conducted using Hayes process in SPSS. Relationship of physical health problems and presenteeism among employees in public sector manufacturing organisations is moderated by marital status variable was analysed. The model summary recommends that physical health problems and interaction of marital status mutually explains 4.36% variance in presenteeism. The p -value=.0009 of the model shows that model is statistically significant. The moderating analysis with gender shows a p -value of .0062 ($P < .05$) and LLCI (-.5098) and ULCI (-.0849) values. These values indicate marital status working as a moderator in between physical health problems and presenteeism. The analysis shows that conditional effects is significant for low ($P = .0002$) and not significant for high

($P=.7251$). The moderator marital has a significant conditional effect on relationship between physical health problems and presenteeism (Table No: 12) and the graphical plot depicting conditional effects of marital status are generated (Graph No: 2).

Table No: 12
Physical health problems and presenteeism is moderated by marital status

```

Run MATRIX procedure:
***** PROCESS Procedure for SPSS Version 3.5 *****
      Written by Andrew F. Hayes, Ph.D.   www.afhayes.com
      Documentation available in Hayes (2018). www.guilford.com/p/hayes3
*****
Model : 1
  Y : PST
  X : PHT
  W : Martlsts

Sample Size: 375
*****
OUTCOME VARIABLE: PST
Model Summary
      R      R-sq    MSE      F      df1    df2      p
      .2088   .0436  20.6487   5.6368   3.0000  371.0000   .0009
Model
      coeff    se      t      p    LLCI    ULCI
constant  21.0777   .2374  88.7864   .0000  20.6109  21.5445
PHT        .1170   .0381   3.0695   .0023   .0420   .1919
Martlsts   .4766   .7154   .6661   .5057  -.9302   1.8834
Int_1     -.2973   .1080  -2.7521   .0062  -.5098  -.0849

Product terms key:
Int_1 :   PHT   x   Martlsts

Test(s) of highest order unconditional interaction(s):
      R2-chng    F    df1    df2    p
X*W   .0195   7.5740   1.0000  371.0000   .0062
-----
      Focal predict: PHT   (X)
      Mod var: Martlsts (W)
Conditional effects of the focal predictor at values of the moderator(s):
      Martlsts   Effect    se      t      p    LLCI    ULCI
      -.3367   .2171   .0570   3.8076   .0002   .1050   .3292
      .0000   .1170   .0381   3.0695   .0023   .0420   .1919
      .3367   .0169   .0480   .3520   .7251  -.0774   .1112

Moderator value(s) defining Johnson-Neyman significance region(s):
      Value   % below  % above

```

.1389 96.2667 3.7333

Conditional effect of focal predictor at values of the moderator:

Martlst	Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
-.9600	.4024	.1165	3.4553	.0006	.1734	.6315
-.8600	.3727	.1063	3.5061	.0005	.1637	.5817
-.7600	.3430	.0963	3.5626	.0004	.1537	.5323
-.6600	.3132	.0864	3.6244	.0003	.1433	.4832
-.5600	.2835	.0768	3.6897	.0003	.1324	.4346
-.4600	.2538	.0676	3.7531	.0002	.1208	.3867
-.3600	.2240	.0589	3.8012	.0002	.1081	.3399
-.2600	.1943	.0511	3.8041	.0002	.0939	.2947
-.1600	.1646	.0445	3.7008	.0002	.0771	.2520
-.0600	.1348	.0397	3.3927	.0008	.0567	.2130
.0400	.1051	.0376	2.7941	.0055	.0311	.1791
.1389	.0757	.0385	1.9664	.0500	.0000	.1514
.1400	.0754	.0385	1.9565	.0512	-.0004	.1511
.2400	.0456	.0423	1.0798	.2809	-.0375	.1287
.3400	.0159	.0482	.3300	.7416	-.0789	.1107
.4400	-.0138	.0556	-.2488	.8037	-.1232	.0955
.5400	-.0436	.0640	-.6808	.4964	-.1694	.0823
.6400	-.0733	.0730	-1.0039	.3161	-.2169	.0703
.7400	-.1030	.0825	-1.2494	.2123	-.2652	.0591
.8400	-.1328	.0922	-1.4398	.1508	-.3141	.0486
.9400	-.1625	.1022	-1.5904	.1126	-.3634	.0384
1.0400	-.1922	.1123	-1.7119	.0878	-.4131	.0286

Data for visualizing the conditional effect of the focal predictor:

Paste text below into a SPSS syntax window and execute to produce plot.

```
DATA LIST FREE/ PHT Martlst PST .
```

```
BEGIN DATA.
```

```
-6.3353 -.3367 19.5417
.0000 -.3367 20.9172
6.3353 -.3367 22.2927
-6.3353 .0000 20.3365
.0000 .0000 21.0777
6.3353 .0000 21.8189
-6.3353 .3367 21.1312
.0000 .3367 21.2381
6.3353 .3367 21.3451
```

```
END DATA.
```

```
GRAPH/SCATTERPLOT= PHT WITH PST BY Martlst .
```

```
***** ANALYSIS NOTES AND ERRORS *****
```

Level of confidence for all confidence intervals in output: 95.0000

W values in conditional tables are the mean and +/- SD from the mean.

NOTE: The following variables were mean centered prior to analysis: Martlst PHT

```
----- END MATRIX -----
```

Graph No: 2

Moderating effect of marital status on relationship between physical health problems and presenteeism

Physical health problems and its relationship with presenteeism is moderated by qualification

The relationship between physical health problems and presenteeism is moderated by qualification was analysed. The moderating analysis was conducted using Hayes process in SPSS. Relationship of physical health problems and presenteeism among employees in public sector manufacturing organisations is moderated by qualification variable was analysed. The model summary recommends that physical health problems and interaction of qualification mutually explains 2.66 % variance in presenteeism. The p-value=.0184 of the model shows that model is statistically significant. The moderating analysis with qualification shows a p-value of .1600 ($P > .05$) and LLCI (-.0164) and ULCI (.0991) values. These values indicate qualification not working as a moderator in between physical health problems and presenteeism. (Table No: 13).

Table No: 13
Physical health problems and presenteeism is moderated by qualification

```

Run MATRIX procedure:
***** PROCESS Procedure for SPSS Version 3.5 *****
      Written by Andrew F. Hayes, Ph.D.   www.afhayes.com
      Documentation available in Hayes (2018). www.guilford.com/p/hayes3
*****
Model : 1
  Y : PST
  X : PHT
  W : Qualific
Sample Size: 375
*****
OUTCOME VARIABLE: PST
Model Summary
      R      R-sq    MSE      F      df1    df2      p
      .1631   .0266   21.0154   3.3803   3.0000  371.0000   .0184
Model
      coeff      se      t      p    LLCI    ULCI
constant  20.9831   .2368  88.6295   .0000  20.5176  21.4487
PHT        .1055   .0374   2.8196   .0051   .0319   .1791
Qualific   -.1089   .1893   -.5756   .5652   -.4811   .2632
Int_1      .0414   .0294   1.4079   .1600   -.0164   .0991
Product terms key:
Int_1 :    PHT    x    Qualific
Test(s) of highest order unconditional interaction(s):
      R2-chng      F      df1    df2      p
X*W    .0052   1.9822   1.0000  371.0000   .1600
-----
Focal predict: PHT    (X)
Mod var: Qualific (W)
Data for visualizing the conditional effect of the focal predictor:
Paste text below into a SPSS syntax window and execute to produce plot.
DATA LIST FREE/ PHT    Qualific PST    .
BEGIN DATA.
-6.3353  -1.2579  20.7813
.0000  -1.2579  21.1202
6.3353  -1.2579  21.4590
-6.3353  .0000  20.3147
.0000  .0000  20.9831
6.3353  .0000  21.6516
-6.3353  1.2579  19.8481
.0000  1.2579  20.8461

```

```

6.3353  1.2579  21.8441
END DATA.GRAPH/SCATTERPLOT=PHT WITH PST BY Qualific .
***** ANALYSIS NOTES AND ERRORS *****
Level of confidence for all confidence intervals in output: 95.0000
NOTE: The following variables were mean centered prior to analysis: Qualific PHT
----- END MATRIX -----
    
```

Physical health problems and its relationship with presenteeism is moderated by experience

The relationship between physical health problems and presenteeism is moderated by experience was analysed. The moderating analysis was conducted using Hayes process in SPSS. Relationship of physical health problems and presenteeism among employees in public sector manufacturing organisations is moderated by experience variable was analysed. The model summary recommends that physical health problems and interaction of experience mutually explains 9.35 % variance in presenteeism. The p-value=.0000 of the model shows that model is statistically significant. The moderating analysis with experience shows a p-value of .8133 (P>.05) and LLCI (-.0762) and ULCI (.0599) values. These values indicate experience not working as a moderator in between health problems and presenteeism. (Table No: 14).

Table No: 14
Physical health problems and presenteeism is moderated by experience

```

Run MATRIX procedure:
***** PROCESS Procedure for SPSS Version 3.5 *****
Written by Andrew F. Hayes, Ph.D. www.afhayes.com
Documentation available in Hayes (2018). www.guilford.com/p/hayes3
*****
Model : 1
Y : PST
X : PHT
W : Exp
Sample Size: 375
*****
OUTCOME VARIABLE: PST
Model Summary
      R      R-sq    MSE      F      df1      df2      p
    .3058    .0935  19.5709  12.7574   3.0000  371.0000  .0000

Model
      coeff      se      t      p      LLCI      ULCI
constant  20.9911   .2344  89.5443  .0000  20.5301  21.4521
PHT        .0625   .0381   1.6424  .1013  -.0123   .1374
Exp        1.1910   .2184   5.4522  .0000   .7614   1.6205
Int_1     -.0082   .0346  -.2364   .8133  -.0762   .0599
    
```

Product terms key:

Int_1 : PHT x Exp

Test(s) of highest order unconditional interaction(s):

	R2-chng	F	df1	df2	p
X*W	.0001	.0559	1.0000	371.0000	.8133

Focal predict: PHT (X)
Mod var: Exp (W)

Data for visualizing the conditional effect of the focal predictor:

Paste text below into a SPSS syntax window and execute to produce plot.

```
DATA LIST FREE/ PHT Exp PST .
```

```
BEGIN DATA.
```

```
-6.3353 -1.0754 19.2584
.0000 -1.0754 19.7103
6.3353 -1.0754 20.1621
-6.3353 .0000 20.5950
.0000 .0000 20.9911
6.3353 .0000 21.3872
-6.3353 1.0754 21.9316
.0000 1.0754 22.2719
6.3353 1.0754 22.6123
```

```
END DATA.
```

```
GRAPH/SCATTERPLOT=
```

```
PHT WITH PST BY Exp .
```

```
*****ANALYSIS NOTES AND ERRORS*****
```

Level of confidence for all confidence intervals in output: 95.0000

NOTE: The following variables were mean centered prior to analysis: Exp PHT

```
----- END MATRIX -----
```

Physical health problems and its relationship with presenteeism is moderated by family income level

The relationship between physical health problems and presenteeism is moderated by family income level was analysed. The moderating analysis was conducted using Hayes process in SPSS. Relationship of physical health problems and presenteeism among employees in public sector manufacturing organisations is moderated by family income level variable was analysed. The model summary recommends that physical health problems and interaction of family income level mutually explains 3.21% variance in presenteeism. The p-value=.0070 of the model shows that model is statistically significant. The moderating analysis with family income level shows a

p-value of .0534 ($P > .05$) and LLCI (-.0011) and ULCI (.1446) values. These values indicate family income level not working as a moderator in between physical health problems and presenteeism. The analysis shows that conditional effects is not significant for low ($P = .5304$) and significant for high ($P = .0011$). The moderator family income level has no significant conditional effect on relationship between physical health problems and presenteeism (Table No:15).

Table No: 15

Physical health problems and presenteeism is moderated by family income level

```

Run MATRIX procedure:
***** PROCESS Procedure for SPSS Version 3.5 *****
      Written by Andrew F. Hayes, Ph.D.   www.afhayes.com
      Documentation available in Hayes (2018). www.guilford.com/p/hayes3
*****
Model : 1
  Y : PST
  X : PHT
  W : Famincm
Sample Size: 375
*****
OUTCOME VARIABLE: PST
Model Summary
      R      R-sq    MSE      F      df1    df2      p
      .1792   .0321  20.8969  4.1008  3.0000  371.0000  .0070

Model
      coeff    se      t      p    LLCI    ULCI
constant  20.9126   .2385  87.6803  .0000  20.4436  21.3816
PHT        .0938   .0380   2.4653  .0141   .0190   .1686
Famincm   -.0074   .3021  -.0246   .9804  -.6014   .5865
Int_1     .0718   .0370   1.9378  .0534  -.0011   .1446

Product terms key:
Int_1 :   PHT   x   Famincm
Test(s) of highest order unconditional interaction(s):
      R2-chng    F      df1    df2      p
X*W   .0098    3.7549  1.0000  371.0000  .0534
-----
      Focal predict: PHT   (X)
      Mod var: Famincm (W)
Conditional effects of the focal predictor at values of the moderator(s):

      Famincm  Effect    se      t      p    LLCI    ULCI
      -.8537   .0325   .0517   .6280  .5304  -.0692   .1342

```

.0000	.0938	.0380	2.4653	.0141	.0190	.1686
.8537	.1551	.0471	3.2923	.0011	.0625	.2477
Moderator value(s) defining Johnson-Neyman significance region(s):						
Value	% below	% above				
-.2201	65.0667	34.9333				
Conditional effect of focal predictor at values of the moderator:						
Famincm	Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
-1.4080	-.0073	.0674	-.1083	.9138	-.1399	.1253
-1.2080	.0071	.0614	.1148	.9086	-.1137	.1279
-1.0080	.0214	.0558	.3838	.7013	-.0883	.1311
-.8080	.0358	.0506	.7070	.4800	-.0637	.1353
-.6080	.0501	.0460	1.0894	.2767	-.0404	.1406
-.4080	.0645	.0422	1.5264	.1278	-.0186	.1476
-.2201	.0780	.0397	1.9664	.0500	.0000	.1560
-.2080	.0788	.0395	1.9949	.0468	.0011	.1566
-.0080	.0932	.0381	2.4483	.0148	.0183	.1681
.1920	.1076	.0380	2.8285	.0049	.0328	.1823
.3920	.1219	.0394	3.0940	.0021	.0444	.1994
.5920	.1363	.0421	3.2399	.0013	.0536	.2190
.7920	.1506	.0458	3.2907	.0011	.0606	.2406
.9920	.1650	.0503	3.2792	.0011	.0661	.2639
1.1920	.1794	.0555	3.2330	.0013	.0703	.2884
1.3920	.1937	.0611	3.1704	.0016	.0736	.3139
1.5920	.2081	.0671	3.1022	.0021	.0762	.3400
1.7920	.2224	.0733	3.0342	.0026	.0783	.3666
1.9920	.2368	.0797	2.9693	.0032	.0800	.3936
2.1920	.2511	.0863	2.9089	.0038	.0814	.4209
2.3920	.2655	.0931	2.8532	.0046	.0825	.4485
2.5920	.2799	.0999	2.8023	.0053	.0835	.4762
Data for visualizing the conditional effect of the focal predictor:						
Paste text below into a SPSS syntax window and execute to produce plot.						
DATA LIST FREE/ PHT Famincm PST .						
BEGIN DATA.						
-6.3353	-.8537	20.7131				
.0000	-.8537	20.9190				
6.3353	-.8537	21.1248				
-6.3353	.0000	20.3185				
.0000	.0000	20.9126				
6.3353	.0000	21.5067				
-6.3353	.8537	19.9239				
.0000	.8537	20.9063				
6.3353	.8537	21.8886				
END DATA.						
GRAPH/SCATTERPLOT= PHT WITH PST BY Famincm .						
*****ANALYSIS NOTES AND ERRORS*****						
Level of confidence for all confidence intervals in output: 95.0000						

W values in conditional tables are the mean and +/- SD from the mean.

NOTE: The following variables were mean centered prior to analysis: incm PHT

----- END MATRIX -----

Conclusion

Employers are becoming increasingly interested in the concept of presenteeism as a result of the increased health-related costs associated with it. This research aimed to determine the causes of presenteeism and/or provide an explanation for why a sick individual goes to work. The role of different variables related to presenteeism is in under researched area. This study was an attempt to define the role of different variables related to presenteeism. The study expands the literature on presenteeism in such a way that, it gives insights into, health problems as the basic reason for presenteeism and answer why an unhealthy employee showing presenteeism. Presenteeism is a factor that reduces productivity and employee performance. This shows the importance of this research because research tried to study the concept of presenteeism and factors influencing presenteeism. The primary goal of the study was to determine whether or not presenteeism exists in the Indian context, as well as the elements that influence presenteeism. The study was conducted among the employees working in public sector manufacturing organisations. Presenteeism is a concept in which employees will come to work without showing absenteeism due to various consensus factors. The mainstream researches show that presenteeism is coming to work while ill. So in this research, the researcher tried to find out whether there is any relationship between health problems and presenteeism. The researcher chooses age, gender, experience, marital status, qualification and family income level as moderating variable. This research contributing to existing literature on presenteeism based on the findings. The relationship analysis between physical health problems and presenteeism shows that they were related statistically and mental health problems and presenteeism are not related statistically. According to the research gender and marital status works as a moderator in between physical health problem and presenteeism. The age, qualification, family income level and experience were not working as a moderating variable in between physical health problem and presenteeism.

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